

A Study of Comparative Teacher-Freezing of Male and Female Higher Education Teachers

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Abstract— The present study is intended to investigate the teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers. The objective of the study was to compare the teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers on each dimension of teacher-freezing and their overall freezing. A total of 160 higher education teachers with 120 male and 40 female degree college teachers were selected randomly from various higher education institutions of Varanasi region (Varanasi, Jaunpur, Ghazipur and Chandauli districts), Uttar Pradesh, for the study. Teacher-freezing Scale (TFS) developed by Dr Haseen Taj (1996) was administered on sample to assess teacher-freezing of male and female degree college teachers. Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to check the normality of the data set and CR-test was applied to find out significance of difference between mean freezing scores of the two. Findings of the study revealed that male and female higher education teachers show approximately the same level of teacher-freezing overall. Female higher education teachers were found more freeze on physical dimension of teacher-freezing in comparison to their counter part. Further, male and female higher education teachers show approximately the same level of teacher-freezing on intellectual, psychological, social and moral dimensions of teacher-freezing.

Keywords: Teacher-freezing , male, female, degree college teachers, Dimensions of teacher-freezing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education is characterized as strength of a nation. Since independence, education has been an important concern. Government of India introduced several policies and programmes to improve the existing scenario of higher education but we couldn't get expected results. Today, higher education system is facing some serious challenges such as access, equity, quality, autonomy, accountability, affordability, infrastructure, disparity, unsound management and administration etc. Our higher education institutions fail to fulfil the needs, requirements and aspirations of individual, society and nation.

Teachers are the key drivers of higher education. They are deciding factor for quality education. A teacher has to perform variety of tasks such as creating lesson plans, creating a conducive learning environment , instructing students, evaluating performances, working with administrators, interacting with parents, facilitating smooth communication between institution and it's students, institution and parents etc. In performing these tasks efficiently, a teacher requires an umbrella of foundational and advanced skills. Where advanced skills help in enhancing comprehensive understanding, soft skills assist in motivating students towards the intended learning outcomes. In early stage of their services, they try to contribute with full potential. But with the passage of time, they are influenced by circumstantial factors like infrastructure, institutional climate(Hitaishi, Vandana, 2014), student's feedback etc. Poor institutional infrastructure creates inferiority complex among them. Disempowering institutional climate affects their attitude, adjustment and job satisfaction(Massey , J. P., 2011; Cornia & Anghelache, 2012) badly. Ultimately, they got frozen towards their duties.

By the extensive review of related literature, researcher found that there had been conducted a number of studies on teacher-freezing and it's relation with various psychological and personal attributes of teachers and organizational climate of institution. Studies have shown diversity in results. Almost studies have been conducted on secondary school teachers. Therefore, researcher decided to investigate teacher-freezing of higher education teachers.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Method: As per the nature of the study, descriptive survey method was used in the present study because it can be used appropriately in behavioural sciences to describe the characteristics of a population in realistic settings.

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique: The population of present study is made up of degree college teachers of Varanasi region. Stratified random sampling technique was used to draw samples from the population. A total of 160 higher education teachers were taken from different degree colleges of Varanasi region including 120 male and 40 female teachers.

Research Tool: A standardized tool 'Teacher Freezing Scale' developed by Dr Haseen Taj (1996), Department of Education, Bengaluru University, was used to assess the teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers.

Methods of Data Analysis: Shapiro-Wilk test was performed on the data set to ensure the normality of data gathered. As distribution was found normal and interval scale of assessment was used, researcher decided to apply CR-test to check whether the difference between the mean freezing scores of male and female teachers is significant. Researcher decided 0.05 level of significance for statistical analysis.

III. COMPARISON OF TEACHER-FREEZING OF MALE AND FEMALE HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS

Objective-1: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers with respect to sex.

H₀1: There is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of higher education teachers with respect to sex.

Table – 1

CR-test for mean freezing scores of male and female higher education teachers

SI. No.	Sex	N	M	SD	SEM	CR	P
1.	Male	120	246.57	21.37	1.95	0.81	1.98(0.05 level)
2.	Female	40	243.37	22.02	2.01		Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-1 that the estimated CR-value 0.81 was found insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference between teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers. This result shows agreement with the results found by Musheer & Rafaqui (2018) and that of Jain & Chaudhary (2022) who reported insignificant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female secondary school teachers while disagreement with results of Mishra, S. C.(2018) and Basu & Banerjee (2018) who reported male teachers more freeze in comparison to female teachers in secondary schools. Further, this result shows partial agreement with the findings of Jena, P. C.(2018) who reported significant difference in teacher-freezing of science-stream male and female teachers while insignificant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female teachers of art-stream at secondary school level.

IV. COMPARISON OF MALE AND FEMALE HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON INTELLECTUAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective-2: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

Table-2

CR-test for mean freezing scores of male and female higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension

SI. No.	Sex	N	M	SD	SEM	CR	P
1.	Male	120	81.84	5.08	0.46	0.38	1.98(0.05 level)
2.	Female	40	82.20	5.47	0.50		Result: Insignificant

It is evident from the table-2 that the calculated CR-value 0.38 is found insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers on intellectual-freezing dimension.

V. COMPARISON OF MALE AND FEMALE HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON PSYCHOLOGICAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective-3: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

H₀3: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

Table-3

CR-test for mean freezing scores of male and female higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension

SI. No.	Sex	N	M	SD	SEM	CR	P
1.	Male	120	46.58	6.34	0.58	0.01	1.98(0.05 level)
2.	Female	40	46.60	6.67	0.61		Result: Insignificant

It is evident from the table-3 that the calculated CR-value 0.01 is found insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers on psychological-freezing dimension.

VI. COMPARISON OF MALE AND FEMALE HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON SOCIAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective-4: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

H₀4: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

Table-4

CR-test for mean freezing scores of male and female higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension

SI. No.	Sex	N	M	SD	SEM	CR	P
1.	Male	120	39.63	5.12	0.47	0.31	1.98(0.05 level)
2.	Female	40	39.90	2.78	0.25		Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-4 that the calculated CR-value 0.31 is found insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers on social-freezing dimension.

VII. COMPARISON OF MALE AND FEMALE HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON PHYSICAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective-5: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

H₀5: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

Table-5

CR-test for mean freezing scores of male and female higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension

SI. No.	Sex	N	M	SD	SEM	CR	P
1.	Male	120	60.22	5.02	0.46	3.37	1.98(0.05 level)
2.	Female	40	56.87	6.58	0.60		Result: Significant

It is evident from table-5 that the calculated CR-value 3.37 is found significant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is a significant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers on physical-freezing dimension. Female higher education teachers are found more freeze in comparison to male higher education teachers. They show lower level of responsibility to promote quality education and they lack will, time and energy in participating into college administration, meetings and extra-curricular activities in comparison to male teachers.

VIII. COMPARISON OF MALE AND FEMALE HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON MORAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective-6: To compare teacher-freezing of higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

H₀6: There is no significant difference in higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension with respect to sex.

Table-6

CR-test for mean freezing scores of male and female higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension

SI. No.	Sex	N	M	SD	SEM	CR	P
1.	Male	120	18.20	2.37	0.22	0.23	1.98(0.05 level)
2.	Female	40	18.30	2.39	0.22		Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-6 that the calculated CR-value 0.23 is found insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. It indicates that there is no significant difference in teacher-freezing of male and female higher education teachers on moral-freezing dimension.

IX. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

It may be concluded that male and female higher education teachers have approximately the same level of teacher-freezing overall. They differ only on physical dimension of teacher-freezing. Female higher education teachers are more freeze on physical dimension of teacher-freezing in comparison to male higher education teachers.

There may be so many reasons behind the physical-freezing of female higher education teachers. Negative attitude, job dissatisfaction (Kaur & Sidana, 2010), lack of professional and organizational commitment, lack of motivation, burden of domestic responsibilities and traditions & rituals may freeze female higher education teachers(Taj Haseen,1997).

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